

D4.1 Systematic review of ecosystem assessment model uptake for decision-support

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1 Preface

The importance of biodiversity, natural capital and healthy ecosystems and the services they supply has increasingly been acknowledged in diverse policy initiatives (e.g., EU Biodiversity Strategies 2020 and 2030, Intergovernmental Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES), Natural Capital and Ecosystem Services Accounting, Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) and Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)).

The EU Horizon Research and Innovation Action “Science for Evidence-based and sustainable decisions about NATural capital” (SELINA) aims to provide robust information and guidance that can be harnessed by different stakeholder groups to support transformative change in the EU, to halt biodiversity decline, to support ecosystem restoration and to secure the sustainable supply and use of essential Ecosystem Services (ES) in the EU by 2030.

SELINA builds upon the Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystems and their Services (MAES) initiative that has provided the conceptual, methodological, data and knowledge base for comprehensive assessments on different spatial scales, including the EU-wide assessment (Maes, 2020)¹ and assessments in EU member states. Knowledge and data for different ecosystem types are increasingly available.

The overall objective of Work Package (WP) 4 “Ecosystem services mapping and assessment” is to refine the ES knowledge base that is available from prior EU Actions by diagnosing, developing and testing the capabilities of ES assessment approaches, models and indicators that increase the likelihood of uptake in decision-making.

The Deliverable D4.1 “Systematic review of ecosystem assessment model uptake for decision-support” is a manuscript entitled “Increasing uptake of ecosystem service assessments: best practice check-lists for practitioners in Europe” that is submitted to the scientific journal *One Ecosystem*. It builds upon the review of 111 guidance documents on ES assessments presented in Milestone report M08. The paper summarises factors that have been identified to limit the uptake of ES assessment in the decision-making context. Furthermore, it gives guidance for practitioners on how to improve ES assessments in the future aiming at increasing their robustness and hence likelihood of uptake at different governance levels.

¹ Maes, J., et al. (2020). Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystems and their Services: An EU ecosystem assessment. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg. DOI:10.2760/757183, JRC120383.

2 Summary

IPBES reviews of scientific literature revealed a lack of documentation of uptake of ecosystem service assessment in decision-making processes. At the same time, ES assessments are increasingly used in EU policy, such as an EU regulation on ecosystem accounting. National level ES assessments have been carried out and the number of guidelines for implementation has been growing during the past decade.

SELINA deliverable 4.1 presents the results of a review of guidance documents on international, national and local applications of ES assessments across Europe. The aim of this review was to compile study design recommendations that are likely to increase the uptake of ES assessments in decision-making. As a first step the project conducted a review of 111 guidance documents on ES assessments covering 12 European languages. Guidance documents were evaluated based on 7 diagnostic topics suggested to increase relevance and robustness of ES assessments: ecosystem condition variables; capacity, potential, supply-demand; spatial scaling and resolution capability; social and health benefit compatibility; economic valuation compatibility and uncertainty assessment. We developed the guidance recommendations across these topics into a set of checklists for practitioners and contractors of ES assessments. These checklists are aimed at projects self-assessing and improving their assessment practice to increase robustness of their ES assessment.

The checklists presented in this deliverable will be tested and further refined in task 4.2, by applying them to case studies of ecosystem services assessment in collaboration with the SELINA Demonstration Projects and test sites. They will then form part of the SELINA knowledge base that will be used to produce guidelines for enabling ES uptake in project and policy cycles.

1 **Version:** Submission One Ecosystem (Pensoft)

2 **Title:** *Increasing uptake of ecosystem service assessments: best practice check-lists for*
3 *practitioners in Europe*

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16 **Abstract**

17 Aiming at understanding the role of plural values in decision-making the IPBES Values Assessment
18 defined nature valuation broadly as including biophysical, economic and socio-cultural assessments,
19 including ecosystem service assessment. IPBES reviews of scientific literature revealed a lack of
20 documentation of uptake by stakeholders across method types. At the same time, ES assessments
21 are increasingly used in EU policy, such as an EU regulation on ecosystem accounting. National level
22 ES assessments have been carried out and the number of guidelines for implementation has been
23 growing during the past decade. The EU project SELINA aims to contribute to increasing uptake of ES
24 assessments at different governance levels. The project is undertaking a series of steps to increase the
25 use of guidance in national and local applications by compiling study design recommendations for ES
26 assessments across Europe and then testing them in demonstration projects around Europe. As a first
27 step the project conducted a review of 111 guidance documents on ES assessments covering 12
28 European languages. Guidance documents were evaluated based on 7 diagnostic topics suggested to
29 increase relevance and robustness of ES assessments: ecosystem condition variables; capacity-
30 potential, supply-demand; spatial scaling and resolution capability; social and health benefit
31 compatibility; economic valuation compatibility and uncertainty assessment. We developed the
32 guidance recommendations across these features into a set of checklists for practitioners and
33 contractors of ES assessments. We discuss possible synergies between these study design features,
34 and gaps in guidance in relation to the policy cycle. Checklists are aimed at projects self-assessing and
35 improving their assessment practice to increase robustness of their ES assessment. From a knowledge
36 supply perspective this is expected to increase the likelihood of uptake of results by stakeholders.
37 However, we end the paper with some cautions on limitations to uptake from different perspectives
38 and the demand of and political uses of ES assessment knowledge.

39 **Keywords**

40 ecosystem condition, social benefits, health benefits, economic valuation, ecosystem accounting,
41 spatial scale, spatial resolution, ecosystem capacity, ecosystem potential, uncertainty

42

43 1. Introduction

44 Mapping and assessment of ecosystem services includes biophysical, socio-cultural and economic
45 techniques (Santos-Martin et al. 2018). With the aim of understanding the role of plural values in
46 decision-making, the IPBES Values Assessment (VA) identified biophysical, monetary and socio-cultural
47 value indicators all as types of valuations of nature (Termansen et al. 2022). The IPBES VA argued that
48 understanding how methods to assess nature, including biophysical assessments, represent different
49 kinds of broad and specific values and value indicators can help explain stakeholders use of different
50 types of knowledge (Pascual et al. 2023).

51 Two IPBES VA reviews of the scientific literature independently revealed a lack of documentation of
52 uptake across method types, including ES assessments (Barton et al. 2022; Termansen et al. 2022).
53 Several recent reviews of scientific literature on the assessment of ecosystems and their services in
54 the last decade have had similar findings (Chan and Satterfield 2020; Laurans et al. 2013; Mandle et al.
55 2020; Saarikoski et al. 2018). ‘Documented uptake’ refers here to scientific publications reporting on
56 use of assessment outputs by stakeholders (Barton et al. 2022). Findings by Laurans et al. (2013) of as
57 little as 2% of economic ecosystem service valuation documenting uptake showed little signs of
58 improvement in the reviews by the IPBES VA a decade later (Barton et al. 2022; Termansen et al. 2023).
59 The IPBES VA identified potential blindspots with regard to legitimacy, credibility, salience, timeliness,
60 process documentation, and study cost to explain lacking uptake of assessments (Barton et al. 2022).
61 In their synthesis of the IPBES VA findings, Pascual et al. (2023) recommend increasing relevance by
62 clearly defining purpose and targeting assessment in relation to stages in the policy cycle.

63 The findings on uptake from the scientific literature reviews contrasts with recent developments at the
64 EU policy. The EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 (EC 2020) calls for developing an EU-wide
65 methodology to map, assess, and achieve good condition of ecosystems, so they can deliver benefits
66 to society through the provision of ecosystem services. (Vallecillo et al. 2022) propose an EU-wide
67 methodology for ecosystem condition building on the Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystems and
68 their Services (MAES) and related integrated framework (B Burkhard and Maes 2017). The MAES
69 framework includes different methods of ES quantification using, biophysical, monetary and social-
70 cultural approaches. The first EU mapping and assessment of ecosystems and their services was
71 conducted in 2020 (EC 2020). Planning is underway for the second EU ecosystem assessment in 2026.
72 MAES were initially carried out for the purpose of generally informing, awareness raising and agenda-
73 setting among the public, in business and government (e.g. Schröter et al., 2016). The policy cycle
74 has evolved during the last decade to MAES increasingly being recognised as supporting EU policy
75 frameworks such as the Biodiversity Strategy and in specific regulation, such as environmental
76 economic accounting and the Nature Restoration Law.

77
78 The European Parliament reached an agreement on the EU Nature Restoration Law for a target of
79 restoring 20% of the EUs land and sea by 2030. Some of the law’s specific targets refer to indicators
80 of ES (e.g., enhance stock of organic carbon), and others to ecosystem condition variables (e.g., amount
81 of deadwood in forests, no net loss of green space in urban ecosystems by 2030, total increase by
82 2040). Member states will have to adopt targets in national restoration plans. The implementation of
83 this law will require practitioners guiding EU Member States to do ES assessments that address no net
84 loss and positive gain targets.

85 Ecosystem services assessment lies at the core of standardisation of ecosystem accounting (UN 2021)
86 in the EU and member states. Recent signs of increased uptake at EU policy level include EUROSTATs
87 collaboration with national statistical offices on a proposal for the amendment of the EU regulation
88 691/2011 on environmental economic accounts. The amendment covers ecosystem type extent for all

89 ecosystem types, a selection of condition variables and biophysical ecosystem service accounts to be
90 estimated in selected ecosystem types. User friendly tools and guides for national level
91 implementation of ES models are being developed, such as the INCA Tool (Buchhorn et al. 2022). Key
92 bottlenecks in method implementation have been identified in the SEEA EA research agenda (UN 2021).
93 Legitimacy of national level ecosystem accounts will in part depend on methods being not only robust
94 and resource efficient from the ‘knowledge supply side’, but also relevant for the ‘knowledge demand
95 side’ by sub-national and local governance actors.

96 Burkhard et al. (2018) called for integrated ecosystem assessment linking biophysical assessment to
97 human well-being within complex interlinked Social-Ecological Systems. Their integrated MAES
98 framework proposed nine steps focused on spatially explicit ecosystem types, condition and services
99 mapping that could be used ‘to set-up related research and development initiatives and to guide
100 involved scientists, decision-makers and practitioners’ (op.cit). The integrated MAES framework
101 recognises that the demand for ES assessment is determined by a complex system, but Burkhard et al.
102 (2018) do not address the detail of what linking to SES entails. Socio-ecological systems (SES) include
103 ‘governance systems’ and ‘actors’ acting withing ‘social, economic and political settings’ (McGinnis and
104 Ostrom 2014). Assessment of ecosystem services in social ecological systems, faces challenges to
105 uptake as does valuation of nature more broadly (Barton et al. 2022). The plural valuation approach of
106 the IPBES VA can complement biophysical ES assessment in the MAES framework, by recognising
107 biophysical metrics as one set of values and designing an assessment process that also recognises
108 stakeholders other plural values (Pascual et al. 2023; Termansen et al. 2023).

109
110 This paper aims to strengthen the recent trend in increased uptake at EU level by collating guidance
111 for sub-national applications. It aims to identify common ecosystem service assessment design
112 recommendations intended to increase uptake. The IPBES VA reviews of uptake of nature valuation
113 (Barton et al. 2022; Termansen et al. 2023) did not address “grey” literature, such as guidance
114 documents. This paper addresses this gap by reviewing best practice recommendations in guidance
115 documents in different European languages, which were evaluated based on selected diagnostic
116 topics, as described in Section 2. Based on the review we formulate a sets of checklist questions to
117 support practitioners in carrying out a diagnostic of ES assessments. In order to identify blindspots in
118 these recommendations we also evaluate the checklist questions in relation to their relevance for
119 different steps of a policy cycle, and compare them to the IPBES VA 5-step framework for plural
120 valuation (Termansen et al. 2023). The paper is part of ongoing work in the EU project SELINA
121 (<https://project-selina.eu/>) to develop guidance for the project’s ES assessment demonstration
122 projects in partner countries.

123 **2. Identifying diagnostic topics to improve uptake of ES assessments**

124 In this section we describe how we develop the MAES framework and its integration with social-
125 ecological systems through 7 diagnostic topics. The diagnostic topics are also aim at increase likelihood
126 of uptake by improving robustness and relevance from the ‘knowledge supply side’. The diagnostic
127 topics aim to strengthen both the biophysical assessment ‘core’ of the MAES approach, as well as
128 deepen its plural valuation characteristics to better link to different dimensions of welfare in SES:

129 Strengthening biophysical ecosystem service assessment:

- 130
131
- 132 **1. Spatial resolution and scaling capability of assessments.** At the core of the MAES framework is
133 mapping of extent, condition and ecosystem service at compatible scales and resolutions with
134 available data (e.g. Andrew et al., 2015; Frank and Burkhard, 2017; Martínez-López et al., 2019).

135 It involves determining the appropriate spatial scale and resolution at which ecosystem services
136 should be assessed to ensure accuracy and relevance. In practical terms, high spatial resolution
137 allows for more detailed and precise mapping of ecosystem services, which is essential for
138 localized planning and management. Conversely, broader scaling capabilities enable the
139 integration of local data into larger frameworks, aiding in regional or national policy development
140 and decision-making. The challenge lies in balancing the need for detailed local data with the
141 broader perspective required for large-scale environmental management

142 2. **Ecosystem condition in ecosystem service assessment.** Ecosystem service assessments have the
143 potential to be more relevant and robust by being sensitive to changes in both ecosystem extent
144 and condition (e.g. Broszeit et al., 2017; Bruins et al., 2017; Kim et al., 2023). This aspect of
145 ecosystem service assessment emphasizes the importance of evaluating the condition or health
146 of ecosystems as a critical factor in understanding and quantifying the services they provide.
147 Ecosystem condition refers to the quality and functionality of an ecosystem, which directly
148 impacts its ability to deliver ES. Considering ecosystem condition in ecosystem service
149 assessments provides a more holistic and accurate understanding of the capacity of ecosystems
150 to deliver services.

151 3. **Identifying ecosystem service capacity, potential, supply-use and demand** is recommended to
152 understand mismatches between supply and demand, assess sustainability of use and determine
153 the lifetime of ecosystems as assets in accounting (e.g. Dworczyk and Burkhard, 2021; Hein et al.,
154 2016). This aspect of ES assessment focuses on quantifying and understanding the actual usage
155 and demand by human societies. Each component plays a vital role in sustainable ecosystem
156 management and policy-making. Balancing these aspects is essential for understanding and
157 managing the mismatches between what ecosystems can sustainably offer (capacity and
158 potential) and what is required or desired by human populations (demand). By identifying these
159 disparities, decision-makers can implement strategies to ensure sustainable usage, protect
160 ecosystem condition, and maintain the long-term viability of ecosystem services.

161 4. **Uncertainty documentation** in all steps of assessment of ecosystem services aims at
162 communicating robustness, increasing stakeholder trust, an uptake of results in policy (e.g. Bryant
163 et al., 2018; Hamel and Bryant, 2017; Hou et al., 2013; Lautenbach et al., 2019; Schulp and
164 Landuyt, 2017). Uncertainty in ecosystem service assessments can arise from various sources,
165 including data limitations (e.g., gaps in data, variability in data quality), model uncertainties (e.g.,
166 assumptions, simplifications), and inherent variability in ecological systems. It can also stem from
167 socio-economic factors, such as changing land-use patterns or economic fluctuations. Methods
168 to document and address uncertainty include statistical analysis, scenario planning, sensitivity
169 analysis, and using a range of models or approaches to cross-verify results. Moreover, clearly
170 communicating these uncertainties, both in scientific publications and in more accessible formats
171 for policymakers and the public, is key to ensuring that the findings of ecosystem service
172 assessments are understood and used appropriately.

173 Strengthening plural valuation:

174 5. **Compatibility of ES assessment with economic valuation** has been a persistent challenge (Boyd
175 et al. 2015) and is in focus in operationalising ecosystem accounting (NCAVES and MAIA 2022).
176 Economic valuation methods that are sensitive to both ecosystem service and condition metrics
177 are expected to be more valid and reliable in value transfer for multiple decision support
178 applications (Grammatikopoulou et al. 2023; Johnston et al. 2021)

179 6. **Compatibility with social benefits and justice assessment** will make ES assessments more
180 relevant for local communities and by addressing justice issues such as unequal access to services

181 can facilitate more inclusive and legitimate assessment processes (e.g. Calderón-Argelich et al.,
 182 2021; Gould et al., 2020; Loos et al., 2023; Schaafsma et al., 2023)
 183 **7. Compatibility with health benefit assessment** further extends ES assessments relevance for
 184 human welfare (e.g. Oosterbroek et al., 2016; Remme et al., 2021). Demonstrating human health
 185 impacts of ecosystem degradation is also a strategy for mobilizing wider sector policy support for
 186 values of nature (Pascual et al. 2023)

187
 188 **3. Methods and materials**

189 In this section we first describe the materials of the guidance document review, and then describe the
 190 IPBES Values Assessment policy cycle and 5 steps of plural valuation used to further classify the
 191 diagnostic topic checklists.

192 **3.1 Materials**

193 The assessed guidance documents were chosen because they describe current best practices and
 194 advised methods for ES assessment in Europe. Guidance documents can be reports resulting from
 195 research projects, official policy documents for national assessments, instruction manuals written for
 196 specific management programs or for a range of other applications. However, one common factor is
 197 that there is no common repository for these. Therefore, the review team collected documents by
 198 using expert knowledge on the latest state-of-the-art in using ES assessment for supporting European
 199 policy and decision making. Experts were from 50 project partners in the EU SELINA project in 27
 200 member state and Norway, Switzerland, the UK and Israel. During the document collection period,
 201 SELINA members could submit any document they considered a relevant guidance document and,
 202 based on scanning the document, marked them for relevance for each of the diagnostic topics. The
 203 following requirements were placed on whether a document was relevant for the review:

- 204 ● The document ideally should not be published before 2018.
- 205 ● The document could be in any of the languages of SELINA partners.
- 206 ● The document must address at least one of the diagnostic topics as described in Table
 207 1 in the context of ES assessment.

208 122 documents were collected for review. These were written in either English, Bulgarian, Croatian,
 209 Danish, Dutch, Estonian, French, German, Hungarian, Norwegian, Polish or Swedish. Five of the
 210 documents were unavailable for download and six were not guidance documents but peer-reviewed
 211 scientific publications, leaving 111 guidance documents to be distributed among the diagnostic topic
 212 groups for review. Each document could be marked as relevant for multiple topics, leading to a final
 213 number of reviewed documents per topic as shown in Table 1. For a full overview of all 111 documents
 214 included in the review, see Supplement S8.

215 **Table 1 Distribution of guidance documents for review across diagnostic topics**

Diagnostic topic	Number of documents reviewed
Spatial scaling and resolution capabilities	74
Ecosystem condition variables in ES models	59
Capacity, potential & actual supply, use, demand	80
Economic valuation compatibility	56
Social benefit compatibility and dimensions of justice	48
Health benefit compatibility	44

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217 Each diagnostic topic was assessed independently by groups of 5-7 co-authors. Each diagnostic topic
218 group developed a survey in Google Forms for reviewing the documents. For each diagnostic topic
219 these surveys aimed to cover to what extent it was addressed in the guidance document, how it
220 defined the topic, and to what extent the guidance was specific to certain stages of the policy cycle
221 (section 3.2).

222 All groups summarised their findings into a working paper (Immerzeel et al., 2023). Each review team
223 for diagnostic topics reworked the recommendations in the working paper into one checklist of
224 questions per diagnostic topic. The checklist questions were classified into one of the 5 plural valuation
225 steps by each review team (section 3.3). Each recommendation checklist was collated to provide an
226 overview of thematic coverage across the assessment steps and the relative knowledge gaps across
227 steps. The review teams discussed potential knowledge gaps in the guidance documents from their
228 perspectives as ES assessment practitioners. These knowledge gaps were then formulated as additional
229 batteries of checklist questions. Each group formulated hypotheses about linkages and synergies
230 between the 7 diagnostic topics in ES assessment – linkages are visualised in a network diagram.
231 Finally, limitations and potential for testing in real world use cases was discussed by each group.
232 Narratives of each review team’s approach can be found in Supplements S1-S7.

233 **3.2 Methods – policy cycle framework**

234 We also assess the extent to which EU guidance documents cover different ‘political settings’ defined
235 here by stages in a *policy cycle* (IPBES 2022; Pascual et al. 2023). Step of the policy cycle are defined
236 as (1) aiding agenda setting and support to agreed goals; (2) providing technical assistance for policy
237 formulation by, for example, agreeing on the alternatives under consideration, or the design of
238 economic incentives, such as payments for ecosystem services (PES); (3) supporting decisions for policy
239 adoption and assessing cost-effectiveness of alternatives for policy action; (4) facilitating adjustments
240 to implementation measures or budget allocations; and (5) helping undertake retrospective policy
241 evaluation (Pascual et al. 2023). Did ES assessment guidance favour any particular stage of the cycle?
242 We classified recommendations in the guidance documents in relation to the above stages of the policy
243 cycle (**Figure 1**).

244

245

246

247 **Figure 1 Policy cycle and potential entry points for uptake of ES assessments. Source: Pascual et al.**
 248 **2023 .**

249 In principle the recommendations and checklist questions could be applied at any time during a policy
 250 cycle, but certain study design features are more important than others depending on when and the
 251 kind of policy support needed at that time. Review teams screened all the diagnostic topics according
 252 to the frequency by which recommendations could be associated with a particular policy cycle stage.
 253 In the results section we report the 1st and 2nd most frequently cited policy stages by the guidance
 254 documents. This coarse scanning of guidance documents provides a sketch of where the strength of
 255 guidance for ES assessment currently lies.

256

257 **3.3 Methods - plural valuation framework**

258 The review of guidance documents sorted recommendations into the 7 ‘diagnostic’ topics. These were
259 reformulated to a series of checklists for ES assessment practitioners and commissioners. The aim of
260 checklists is to support a practitioner who has a preselection of methods under consideration and/or
261 is designing their implementation. Before the final study design and data collection, the practitioner
262 wants to do a check of whether the valuation process has the characteristics likely to increase uptake.
263 During a study, practitioners may also wish to conduct an internal audit of their study process to check
264 progress against planned study design. The use of checklists can also make it easier for external parties
265 to question and if necessary, contest the study, thereby increasing legitimacy and potential for uptake.
266 In the case of a commissioner of an ecosystem service assessment, the checklist can serve as a guide
267 to doing a “due diligence” evaluation of terms of reference for a study, before putting it out for tender.
268

269 Do our checklist questions for each diagnostic topic address plural valuation recommendations?
270 Drawing from the IPBES Values Assessment, Termansen et al. (2023) recommend a 5-step valuation
271 framework to embed plural values in decision-making (**Figure 2**).

272
273
274 *Figure 2. General IPBES 5-step valuation framework to be applied to ES assessment. Source: based*
275 *on Termansen et al. (2023)*

276 The 7 diagnostic topics can potentially contribute to strengthening ES assessment in any of the five
277 steps. We used the following definitions of the plural valuation steps to further classify the checklist
278 questions:

279 (1) **Invest in a legitimate process**, to ensure that the providers of assessment information are explicitly
280 defined, and that there is transparency in the robustness of the assessment, particularly regarding
281 representativeness and participation.

282 (2) **Define the purpose with stakeholders**, with certain societal goals and decision-making purposes.

283 (3) **Establish the scope**, identifying which metrics will be explored or addressed by the assessment.
284 IPBES VA emphasises that different ecosystem service assessment metrics represent different value
285 types.

286 (4) **Choose and apply methods**, that realise, recognise and represent the full extent of value diversity
287 entailed by the purpose.

288 (5) **Communicate results to inform decisions**, with effective and transparent communication, that is
289 also an honest reflection of the limitations and omissions of the assessment process.

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295 **4. Results of the guidance document review**

296 In this section we first present an overview of the coverage of ES assessment guidance documents of
297 the policy cycle. Second we present the checklist questions for each diagnostic topic derived from the
298 guidance documents, and classify them according to plural valuation steps.

299 **4.1 Guidance coverage of the policy cycle.**

300 The policy cycle stages best covered by guidance are agenda setting, policy formulation and policy
301 implementation. The least covered are policy evaluation and policy adoption. Supporting choice
302 between options and evaluating those choices are forms of decision-support. Broadly speaking, ES
303 assessment guidance literature is the least rich in terms of ex ante supporting choice between policy
304 options and ex post evaluating the outcomes of those options. This relative knowledge gap was also
305 reflected by the IPBES VA review finding that a majority of nature valuation studies made only cursory
306 reference to their relevance for decision-support (Barton et al. 2022).

307

308

309 **Figure 3. Policy cycle stages with best coverage in ES guidance.** Note: diagnostic topics are assigned to
310 the policy cycle stage at which they were referred to 1st and 2nd most frequently in the guidance review by
311 Immerzeel et al. 2023. Source: adapted from Pascual et al. 2023 .

312 **4.2 Diagnostic check lists**

313 The results of the grey literature review are presented as a series of checklists for practitioners covering
314 the 7 ES assessment diagnostic topics. The full-length checklists can be found in Supplementary
315 Material S1-S7. In next steps the checklists will be tested and validated in real world ES applications
316 within the EU SELINA project. Validation will entail researchers and stakeholders in each application

317 case determining testing whether the checklist questions identify assessment design features that are
 318 likely to increase uptake. The validation of these checklists is beyond the scope of this paper.

319 **Figure 4** visualises this two-dimensional classification – there is a variable number of questions per
 320 diagnostic topic, as derived from the guidance document review. The number of checklist questions
 321 per diagnostic topic presents the relative richness of recommendations in the guidance documents
 322 reviewed. Note that the relative number of checklist questions *is not* proportional to the number of
 323 guidance documents that were reviewed per topic (**Table 1**). For example, the smallest number of
 324 guidance questions was derived from the topic with the largest number of documents reviewed
 325 (capacity-potential[.]), whereas the topic with smallest number of reviewed documents resulted in a
 326 comprehensive checklist (uncertainty documentation).

327

DIAGNOSTIC TOPICS FROM GUIDANCE REVIEW						
Spatial scaling and resolution enabled ES assessment	Ecosystem condition enabled ES assessment	Capacity-potential, supply-use-demand in ES assessment	Economic valuation compatible ES assessment	Social benefits & justice dimensions compatible ES assessment	Health benefits compatible ES assessment	Uncertainty documentation of ES assessment
Is there a process in place for validating the spatial...	Does the study aim to:	Does the study rely on the analysis of...	Does the study include time and...	Does the study use a participatory...	Have the views of local stakeholders...	Does the study validate the ES...
Are the spatial scale and extent of...	a. Advocate for ensuring access...	Does the study rely on the analysis...	Does the study provide training for...	Does the study aim to understand...	Have the views of local stakeholders...	Does the study use multiple models...
Does the spatial scale of the ES...	b. Enhance the knowledge and...	Does the study offer stepwise...	Are the beneficiaries of each...	Does the study identify ES...	Does the study design allow for...	Does the study perform model...
Are the spatial units used in the...	c. Develop standardised...		Does the study discuss the...	Does the study compare/validate...	Have distinct pathways between...	Does the study use data of...
Are spatially explicit indicators used...	d. Develop user-friendly tools...		Is it possible to expand the scope of...	Has a mechanism been established...	Does the study include an...	Does the study use scenarios?
Are spatially explicit indicators used...	e. Encourage participation and...		Does the study discuss the...		Does the study include an...	Does the study monitor risks?
Is the spatial resolution of the...	f. Highlight priority ecosystem...		Does the study use a biophysical...		Has a mechanism been established...	Does the study include contingency...
Does the assessment take into...	g. Promote restoration targets...		Do the scales (temporal, spatial,...		Does the study include an...	Does the study use the...
Is the spatial resolution of the...	h. Establish clear indicators for...		Does the study describe and...			Does the study communicate...
	Does the study present well-defined...		Does the study assess and address...			Does the study collect information...
	Does the study emphasise the...		Does the study develop...			Does the study take uncertainty into...
	Does the study involve the...		Does the study develop...			
	Does the study recommend utilising...		Does the study organise events...			
	Does the study provide guidelines...		Does the study organise meetings at...			
	Does the study present practical...		Does the study publicly report the...			

328
 329 **Figure 4 Checklist questions per diagnostic topic (columns) from the guidance document review,**
 330 **classified by plural valuation steps (colour coding).** For illustrative purposes the small print in the
 331 table represents individual checklist questions – to read checklist questions in normal font please refer
 332 to supplements S1-S7.

333 Some broad thematic patterns can be discerned from the classification. Spatial scaling and resolution
 334 guidance does not provide recommendations on the ‘purpose’ of assessments. This can perhaps be
 335 explained by spatial scale and resolution being general features that must be adapted to any ES
 336 assessment purpose. Guidance on the topics of ‘ecosystem condition’ and ES ‘capacity-potential-
 337 supply-use-demand’ did not cover recommendations for ‘investing in a legitimate assessment process’.
 338 This supports the hypothesis that assessment guidance on biophysical methods of condition and
 339 ecosystem services is largely focused on scientific-technical study design issues, not addressing
 340 stakeholder benefits. This may indicate a relative knowledge gap with respect to making biophysical
 341 assessment directly relevant for stakeholders’ decision-support needs. On the other hand, all of the
 342 ES assessment outcomes related to benefits (economic, social, health) have checklist
 343 recommendations on engaging stakeholders in the assessment process.

344 In the following we provide a narrative summary of the checklist questions through the lens of the
 345 plural valuation steps. We comment on elements that are specific to ecosystem service assessment
 346 and contrast them with the recommendations on plural valuation from the IPBES VA, as summarised
 347 by Termansen et al. (2023).

348 **Invest in a legitimate process.** The review of ES guidance documents recommends a participatory
349 approach that validates and grounds the classification and spatial representation of ecosystem services
350 in the needs, perspectives, knowledge and values of people who rely on the ecosystem services. The
351 process should make it possible for stakeholders to also contribute to the design of the assessment as
352 it proceeds, and to evaluate the predicted outcomes of ES assessment in the policy cycle after the
353 study is completed. This is resource demanding and requires adequate time and budgets. Despite
354 these broadly useful points in line with plural valuation, our review showed that guidance specific to
355 designing an ES assessment process is limited, especially for biophysical assessments. Comparing to
356 IPBES VA recommendations we can note that adapting ES classification and representation to local
357 stakeholder perceptions is a recommendation that may be at odds with the standardised ES
358 classifications such as CICES or ecosystem accounting at national level (IPBES 2022). Furthermore,
359 ecosystem services assessment guidance focuses on relevance to humans, whereas legitimacy in a
360 plural valuation process also considers non-human individuals, groups and communities (Termansen
361 et al. 2023).

362 **Define the purpose.** With the exception of checklists for ecological condition, the review of guidance
363 documents provided limited advice in defining different purposes of ES assessment. Understanding
364 context specific policy and social needs is required to identify the data needed for assessing capacity,
365 supply and demand. Specifying purpose can increase the cost-effectiveness of the ES assessment by
366 calibrating data use to the minimum requirements for robustness for a specific purpose, while
367 considering available resources. Through the policy cycle, the method and data infrastructure
368 development, advocacy & awareness raising, policy design, decision-support, implementation &
369 management, and ex post policy impact evaluation all have different requirements for robustness that
370 need to be understood before starting ES assessment. In the IPBES VA understanding the purpose of
371 the assessment goes beyond simple identification of where in the policy cycle the assessment finds
372 itself. It should also include an understanding of which stakeholders are being addressed and their
373 decision-making roles. Also, understanding is needed of the policy windows for ES assessment
374 outcomes to be able to influence decisions, and the constraints on decision-making procedures
375 impacting nature (Termansen et al. 2023).

376 **Establish the scope.** Existing guidance on ES assessment is limited in its interpretation of 'scope' to
377 the considerations of spatial scaling and resolution. The spatial scale and extent of the ecosystem
378 services assessment should align with the management or policy decision to be assessed and be
379 defined explicitly before methods are chosen. Identification of the beneficiaries of each ecosystem
380 service is key to identifying economic valuation methods. The initial geographical scope or range of
381 ecosystem services that can be assessed with available data and resources may be incomplete relative
382 to expected impacts of policy. To address such limitations, economic valuation also considers the scope
383 for value transfer from existing study sites. In the IPBES VA the interpretation of scoping to also
384 critically consider the different values held by the stakeholders affected is not predominant in
385 assessment guidance on ecosystem condition and biophysical ecosystem service assessment. In plural
386 valuation the scoping stage also includes inventorying stakeholders, including rightsholders, that are
387 affected by changes in nature, and their instrumental, relational or intrinsic value types affected
388 (Termansen et al. 2023). This promotes a more representative choice of assessment methods.

389 **Choose and apply methods.** ES assessment guidance is diverse in providing recommendations on
390 methods. Method recommendations cutting across diagnostic topics include appropriate choice of
391 spatial resolution of assessments to match both the spatial scale and the required spatial and temporal
392 accuracy demanded by stakeholders for their decision-support purposes. This includes considering
393 potential future changes and the spatiotemporal dynamics that need to be described by the

394 assessment methods. With the notable exception of ecosystem accounting, common knowledge gaps
395 include the lacking treatment of temporal variation in the ES assessments (e.g. Burkhard et al. 2014),
396 and the impacts of temporal mismatches between supply and demand, and ultimately on sustainable
397 use. Guidance documents emphasise the challenge of identifying causal pathways and integrated
398 biophysical model compatibility between ecosystem structure, condition and services. The biophysical
399 metrics used must match the methods for assessing benefits. Doing this is recognised as challenging
400 because interactions across economic, social and health benefits must be acknowledged and
401 controlled for. The risks of integrating assessments across long causal chains, leading to decreasing
402 accuracy, should be acknowledged and reported. Shortening causal chains to look at well-being
403 outcomes directly associated with ecosystem condition is among recommendations in the checklists.

404 The IPBES VA plural valuation recommendations emphasise making and documenting informed
405 method choices, considering trade-offs between relevance, robustness and resource availability;
406 taking into account the previous steps of legitimacy of the assessment process, its purpose and scope.
407 Recent guidances on MAES (e.g. Burkhard et al., 2018; Grêt-Regamey et al., 2017) and Ecosystem
408 Accounting (United Nations, 2022a, 2022b) acknowledge such trade-offs through a tiered approach
409 to method selection. Even with such ‘tiered’ guidance there are risks that those in power to
410 commission the studies, as well as practitioners’ disciplinary and professional biases, may determine
411 method selection. By doing ‘due diligence’ documentation of method selection practitioners can
412 mitigate the risks that the study will not necessarily realise, recognise or represent the full extent of
413 value diversity entailed by the purpose’ as determined by a legitimate valuation process (Termansen
414 et al. 2023).

415 **Communicate results to inform decision-makers.** Our review of ES assessment guidance also shows
416 ample recommendations on both direct communication of results, as well as mechanisms for
417 increasing uptake once the assessment is completed. Common recommendations refer to
418 communicating outcomes in maps which clearly show the spatial resolution of ES indicators and
419 resolution and variation of the input data. Standardising the communication of model assumptions
420 and levels of uncertainty is also a general recommendation. Recommendations also include iterative
421 assessment of ecosystem-based adaptive management, as opposed to simple before-after
422 assessment. Meetings with stakeholders and options to make assessment corrections during the study
423 should be considered. Input data can be validated with local communities. Assessments should plan
424 for what happens after the science is completed, including open consultation of results with external
425 audiences. Mechanisms should be in place to hear and record local stakeholders’ feedback. Iterative
426 improvement in ES assessment and adaptive planning should be considered. An iterative, stepwise
427 approach to integrating study results into decision making implies that integrated ES assessment runs
428 through all the stages of a policy cycle. The IPBES VA recommends explicitly evaluating the factors
429 limiting uptake in this process, honest reflection of the limitations and of any omissions in the
430 assessment process. It also recommends that practitioners explicitly provide opportunities for
431 contestation by stakeholder of the conclusions reached (Termansen et al. 2023).

432

433 **5. Discussion**

434 In this section we address the relative blindspots uncovered in current ES guidance recommendations
435 by using extended checklist questions. We discuss the potential interlinkages between assessment
436 design features that can increase uptake. Finally we discuss the policy demand side - how ES
437 knowledge may be taken up in different ways by a political process, independently of how practitioners
438 may supply that knowledge.

439 **5.1 An extended check-list for ES assessment**

440 Each diagnostic topic review group also proposed a number of additional checklist questions to address
 441 relative gaps in checklist questions shown in **Figure 4**. The additional checklist questions were defined
 442 based on the review groups own experience as ES assessment practitioners. The extended checklists
 443 area visualised in **Figure 5** – the full text checklist questions can be found in Supplements S1-S7.

DIAGNOSTIC TOPICS FROM GUIDANCE REVIEW						
Spatial scaling and resolution enabled ES assessment	Ecosystem condition enabled ES assessment	Capacity-potential, supply-use-demand in ES assessment	Economic valuation compatible ES assessment	Social benefits & justice dimensions compatible ES assessment	Health benefits compatible ES assessment	Uncertainty documentation of ES assessment
Is there a process in place for... Are the spatial scale and extent of... Does the spatial scale of the ES... Are the spatial units used in the... Are spatially explicit indicators used... Is the spatial resolution of the... Does the assessment take into... Is the spatial resolution of the... Does the study present well-defined... Does the study emphasise the... Does the study involve the... Does the study recommend utilizing... Does the study provide guidelines... Does the study present practical...	Does the study aim to: a. Advocate for ensuring access... b. Enhance the knowledge and... c. Develop standardized... d. Develop user-friendly tools... e. Encourage participation and... f. Highlight priority ecosystem... g. Promote restoration targets... h. Establish clear indicators for...	Does the study rely on the analysis of... Does the study rely on the analysis... Does the study offer stepwise... Does the study describe and... Does the study explicitly identify... Does the study link and/or integrate... Does the study address... Does the study elucidate the... Does the study explicitly identify... Does the study measure the... Does the study assess and address... Does the study develop... Does the study assess and address... Does the study organise meetings at... Does the study publicly report the...	Does the study include time and... Does the study provide training for... Does the study identify ES... Does the study compare/validate... Is it possible to expand the scope of... Does the study discuss the... Does the study use a biophysical... Does the study describe and... Does the study provide information... Does the study assess and address... Does the study develop... Does the study assess and address... Does the study organise meetings at... Does the study publicly report the...	Does the study use a participatory... Does the study aim to understand... Does the study identify ES... Does the study compare/validate... Has a mechanism been established... Does the study include an... Does the study include an... Does the study evaluate the... Does the study evaluate the...	Have the views of local stakeholders... Have the views of local stakeholders... Does the study design allow for... Have distinct pathways between... Does the study include an... Does the study include an...	Does the study validate the ES... Does the study use multiple models... Does the study perform model... Does the study use data of... Does the study use scenarios?... Does the study monitor risks?... Does the study include contingency... Does the study use the... Does the study communicate... Does the study collect information... Does the study explicitly state the... Does the study take uncertainty into... Does the study take uncertainty into...
ADDITIONAL EXPERT-BASED QUESTIONS TO BE TESTED						
Does the assessment incorporate... Is the third spatial dimension (e.g... Are the methods used to assess... Are common frameworks (e.g. CICES... Are maps of the study area recent... Does the assessment include a... Are the spatial interdependencies... Have potential trade-offs between... Is temporal variability in ecosystem... Are metadata for spatial scales and... Are the limitations on the spatial... Are maps of the study area used to...	Does the study provide clear... Does the study recommend utilizing... Does the study provide guidelines... Does the study present practical...	Does the study rely on the analysis of... Does the study explicitly identify... Does the study link and/or integrate... Does the study address... Does the study elucidate the... Does the study explicitly identify... Does the study measure the... Does the study assess and address... Does the study develop... Does the study assess and address... Does the study organise meetings at... Does the study publicly report the...	Does the study involve stakeholders... Does the study assess long-term... Does the study measure the... Does the study assess and address... Does the study develop... Does the study assess and address... Does the study organise meetings at... Does the study publicly report the...	Does the study investigate the... Does the study customise ES... Does the study identify the most... Does the study acknowledge who... Does the study account for... Does the study evaluate the... Does the study consider the... Does the study explore effective... Does the study aim to sustain long-... Does the study aim to sustain long-...	Have the views of local stakeholders... Have key civil society organisations... Does the study identify the most... Has a long-term role been identified... Does the study address both... Has the study been guided by the... Have specific winners and losers in... Does the study include an... Have the influences of wider social... Does the study identify disparities in... Does the study assess the current... Have the study scenarios / models /... Have indicators been developed... Does the study account for... Has a mechanism been established...	Does the study validate the ES... Does the study use multiple models... Does the study perform model... Does the study use data of... Does the study use scenarios?... Does the study monitor risks?... Does the study include contingency... Does the study use the... Does the study communicate... Does the study collect information... Does the study explicitly state the... Does the study take uncertainty into... Does the study take uncertainty into...

444
 445 **Figure 5 Visualisation of additional checklists to cover knowledge gaps in the ES assessment**
 446 **guidance literature. Note: For illustrative purposes the small print in the table represents individual**
 447 **checklist questions – to read checklist questions in normal font please refer to supplements S1-S7.**

448 Notable characteristics of these extended checklists is the large number of questions added to evaluate
 449 social and health benefits, relative to the recommendations found in the ES guidance literature. The
 450 rationale for this is the relative lack of guidance in particularly for the health sector on how to employ
 451 ecosystem service assessments. A lot of emphasis is placed on additional questions to achieve
 452 legitimate involvement of local communities, and identifying purpose and defining scope that is
 453 compatible with justice dimensions and health outcomes. Notable also are the many additional
 454 checklist questions to address methods gaps in spatial scaling and resolution, and understanding
 455 ecosystem service capacity-potential, supply-use-demand relationships. Guidance on ecological
 456 condition was considered mostly sufficient. Notably, no additional questions were added to

457 uncertainty checklists – at the time of writing this topic was the subject of a separate dedicated review
458 of the scientific literature which had not concluded¹.

459 Given the vast variation in assessment contexts it is not likely that all checklist questions are relevant
460 for each application site. The extended checklists are designed as menus of potentially relevant
461 features for practitioners to use in a ‘self-audit’, aimed at increasing likelihood of uptake. Practitioner
462 and stakeholders collaborating in real world ES assessments can revise and consolidate them to fit
463 their purposes.

464 5.2 Potential interlinkages between study design features and increased likelihood of uptake

465 Diagnostic topic review teams also identified potential synergies between assessment design features
466 (Figure 6). Common to all diagnostic topic groups was the recommendation that spatial and temporal
467 scale and resolution should be explicitly chosen to integrate across ecosystem condition, ecosystem
468 services and economic, social and health benefit outcomes. A second common feature was that
469 adequate definition of ecosystem condition is expected in conjunction to improve the robustness and
470 relevance of ecosystem service and economic, social and health metrics. Specifying ecosystem
471 condition is also expected to improve economic valuation, social justice and health outcome evaluation
472 independently of whether ecosystem service modelling is conducted or not. Thirdly, economic, social
473 and health benefits are mutually determined and should, resources permitting, be assessed together.
474 Fourth, all the above study design features require documentation of uncertainty individually, and also
475 in terms of joint probabilities across integrated ecosystem service assessment.

476

477

478 **Figure 6 Potential synergies between ES assessment features to be tested in real world case**
479 **studies.** Arrows in the diagram represent potential synergies identified by review teams.

480

481

¹ As part of the EU SELINA project: <https://project-selina.eu/> project

482 **5.3. The limitation of checklists - intended purposes of ES assessment versus actual use for political**
483 **interests.** Defining the purpose of ecosystem services assessment can help the practitioner to choose
484 robust methods with the available resources. However, this definition of purposes is from the 'supply'
485 perspective of a knowledge provider. Checklists for assessment design only go as far as the knowledge
486 supplied by the practitioner. Political actors use of the knowledge may mean that actual uptake is
487 determined by power and political expediency. To this end Jacobs et al. (2023) outlines political
488 valuation typologies which can provide an understanding of why ES assessment is not taken up, or
489 even misused, relative to the purpose intended by the practitioner. We briefly paraphrase the Jacobs
490 et al. (op.cit) typology in terms of ecosystem service assessment and comment on its relevance for the
491 diagnostic topics.

492 *Affirmative ES assessment* legitimately represents all stakeholders and recognises their plural values
493 'actively counterbalancing injustices built into history, place, and social arrangements'. This use of ES
494 assessment puts particular emphasis on assessment of social justice dimensions. The checklists in this
495 paper assumes this 'best possible' use case with mutually reinforcement of all the 7 topics of ES
496 assessment design.

497 *Confirmative ES assessment* still brings a diverse set of value to the table, but 'is often applied to justify
498 decisions already taken, and builds credibility and acceptance within broader actor groups'. While
499 practitioners aim to identify biophysical services, economic values, health and social impacts,
500 stakeholders wishing to confirm a status quo may not be favourable to documentation of uncertainty,
501 since it can shed light on knowledge gaps which serve to justify inaction and the status quo power of
502 some actors.

503 Moving away from the ideal contexts of ES assessment in academia, *appropriative ES assessment* sets
504 up an assessment processes to be 'participatory, representative, and/or inclusive, but in the end, a
505 powerful minority uses these qualities to push for an outcome that advances their private benefits'.
506 In such a setting those commissioning an assessment may not want uncertainty documentation
507 because it could cast the foregone conclusions of the study's sponsors into doubt.

508 Moving yet further from an academic ideal, a *repressive assessment* may covertly design an assessment
509 process with potentially opposing actors to 'thereby utilizing their time, energy, and buy-in otherwise
510 available for opposition'. Overtly repressive assessment would even aim to 'discredit or dismiss
511 legitimate claims of opposing actors, as Jacobs et al. put it 'with arguments such as 'actor subjective
512 perceptions' versus 'expert facts'.

513 In *discriminative ES assessment* powerful actors carry out or commission an assessment 'directly in
514 their own interest and use this as a power lever to trump other actors' interests and values'. Such an
515 assessment would not use methods reflecting economic, social or health impacts of societal
516 stakeholders that were not allied with actors in power.

517 The latter political uses could be expected to go undocumented in scientific literature and may seem
518 unusual for practitioners in some European countries. However, Jacobs et al. (2023) typology offers a
519 perspective on the risks of not investing in, or not being allowed to invest in, 'legitimate assessment
520 process' in the first step of an ES assessment.

521

522

523

524 5. Conclusions

525 Mapping and assessment of ecosystem services (MAES) is increasingly used in European and member
526 state policy, such as EU Biodiversity strategy to 2020 and 2030 and the proposed EU regulation on
527 ecosystem accounting. Policy targets for nature positive restoration will also come into force through
528 the EU Nature Restoration Law, requiring assessment of ecosystem services. Recent scientific
529 literature reviews on valuation of nature, including mapping and assessment of ecosystem services
530 (MAES), have at the same time concluded that during the last 20 years there has been a lack of
531 uptake of valuation results by stakeholders for use in decision-support. However, those reviews have
532 not included 'grey literature' such as methodological guidance documents, nor has this been done
533 especially for ecosystem services assessment where future policy demand is expected. We therefore
534 reviewed 111 guidance documents on ES assessment from across Europe. Based on the review we
535 collated guidance recommendations across 7 diagnostic topics aimed at strengthening integrated
536 MAES. We formulated recommendations into checklist questions for each diagnostic topic – the
537 questions are available in method supplements S1-S7. Checklists are aimed at increasing the
538 relevance, robustness and efficiency of knowledge supplied on ecosystem services from practitioners
539 to policy makers.

540 We classified checklist questions according to the policy cycle and the IPBES Values Assessment 5-step
541 recommendations for plural valuation, aiming to strengthen the integration of ES assessment with
542 welfare assessment in social-ecological systems perspective. In relation to the policy cycle, we found
543 that there is relatively little guidance available on supporting policy adoption and policy evaluation,
544 pointing to possibilities for strengthening future methodological guidance work. We examined
545 potential synergies between diagnostic topics. We concluded that identifying ecosystem condition is
546 key to increasing robustness of not only ecosystem service models, but also economic valuation of ES
547 benefits, social and health benefits. Our plural valuation screening also uncovered some knowledge
548 gaps in current guidance, especially in relation to linking ecosystem services to health and social
549 benefits and justice dimensions. We therefore extended checklist questions to cover these and other
550 gaps. Checklist questions available in method supplements will next be tested in collaboration with
551 stakeholders in real world ES applications by the SELINA project. Finally, we recognise that our
552 recommendations are limited to the ES knowledge 'supply side' – likelihood of uptake may be limited
553 by political agendas beyond the awareness and influence of ES assessment practitioners.

554

555

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731 **S1. Ecosystem condition variables in ES assessments**

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	Checklist	Y	N	N R	Comments
1	Does the study aim to:				
	a. Advocate for ensuring access to sufficient funding to support the implementation of new condition assessment approaches/standards, including training and incorporating new professionals?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
	b. Enhance the knowledge and skills of policymakers and supporting scientists/technicians on agreed condition assessment approaches?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
	c. Develop standardised condition assessment methods and accessible, interoperable databases to overcome fragmented data inventory reality faced by policymakers?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
	d. Develop user-friendly tools , such as plugins and software, enabling policymakers and practitioners to analyse, visualise, and interpret data on ecosystem condition and services?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
	e. Encourage participation and collaboration among stakeholders in the design and implementation of strategies like conservation, ecotourism, and monitoring of ecosystems?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
	f. Highlight priority ecosystem condition aspects , services, and their benefits, helping policymakers focus on impactful aspects of their decisions?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
	g. Promote restoration targets based on ecosystem condition needs and emphasise the importance of improving degraded ecosystems?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
	h. Establish clear indicators for ecosystem condition and services at national, regional, or local levels for monitoring and evaluation in policy development?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
2	Does the study present well-defined methods for assessing impacts of ecosystem condition on services?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
3	Does the study emphasise the integration of biodiversity conservation within the evaluation of ecosystem conditions and services?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents

4	Does the study emphasise the integration of well-being assessment within the evaluation of ecosystem conditions and services?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
5	Does the study involve the development of a standardised framework for integrated assessment of ecosystem condition and services to aid policymakers in understanding and utilising information?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
6	Does the study recommend utilising spatial data and maps to visually present ecosystem condition and services data for policymakers?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
7	Does the study provide guidelines for monitoring and evaluating the impacts of ecosystem-based adaptation interventions , such as nature-based solutions or green-blue networks?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
8	Does the study present practical case studies and examples illustrating successful integration of ecosystem condition and services into decision-making processes?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
ADDITIONAL EXPERT-BASED TOPICS					
9	Does the study provide clear definitions and explanations of terms related to ecosystem condition and services, ensuring consistency and better understanding?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise

733 Approach for checklist compilation

734 The checklist for evaluating studies incorporating ecosystem condition variables into ecosystem
735 services models was developed through the examination of guidance documents and leveraged the
736 expertise and experience of the reviewers in this field. The process involved synthesising insights from
737 established methodologies and practical applications found in the guidance document. Assumptions
738 were made based on the belief that **a robust assessment tool should encompass key dimensions**
739 **important for policymakers and practitioners**. These dimensions include clarity of definitions,
740 standardised frameworks, prioritisation of ecosystem aspects, establishment of indicators, promotion
741 of restoration, transparent presentation of methods, integration of biodiversity and well-being, use of
742 spatial data, stakeholder participation, enhancement of policymakers' knowledge, practical case
743 studies, and a call for standardised methods and accessible databases. These assumptions aimed to
744 ensure a comprehensive, practical, and widely applicable checklist, facilitating meaningful integration
745 of ecosystem condition considerations into ecosystem services modelling and ultimately into decision-
746 making processes.

747 Expected limitations and possible steps for improvement

748 While the checklist provides some criteria for evaluating studies incorporating ecosystem condition
749 variables into ecosystem services models, there are some potential limitations when applied to real
750 world cases. Firstly, the checklist assumes a certain level of **data availability** and accessibility, which
751 may vary across ES assessment applications with differing resource constraints. Additionally, the
752 checklist's emphasis on **standardisation** and clear indicators may face challenges in the context of
753 **diverse ecosystems and regional variations**. To enhance its applicability to cases, steps for
754 improvement could involve creating a **tiered system** that accommodates variations in data availability

755 and resource capacities. The checklist could also benefit from **iterative feedback** from case studies to
756 refine and tailor its criteria based on real-world experiences. Furthermore, incorporating flexibility into
757 the checklist to allow for **project-specific adaptations** would enhance its usability across a range of
758 ecological, socio-economic, and political contexts. Regular **updates** based on emerging best practices
759 and technological advancements would ensure the checklist remains a dynamic and relevant tool for
760 guiding ecosystem condition and services assessments in case studies and other applications.

761 **S2. Dimensions of capacity-potential, supply-demand in ES assessment**

762

	Checklist	Y	N	N R	Comments
1	Does the study rely on the analysis of policy needs prior to defining indicators for each of the ES dimension (capacity, supply, demand)? (document #4)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
2	Does the study rely on the analysis of broader (not just accounting use) policy needs prior to defining what input data to and/or outputs to generate? (document #4)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
3	Does the study offer stepwise approaches for assessing ecosystem service capacity, potential supply, actual supply and/or, demand and integrating them into decision-making ?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
ADDITIONAL EXPERT-BASED TOPICS					
4	Does the study rely on the analysis of policy needs prior to defining the ES dimension (capacity, supply, demand)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
5	Does the study explicitly identify and define the concept(s) (capacity, potential supply, actual supply and/or, demand)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
6	Does the study define the concept(s) following an established standard terminology (e.g., Burkhard et al. 2012; Millennium Ecosystem Assessment; CICES; IPBES)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
7	Does the study present clear approaches for assessing each dimension?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
8	Does the study clarify indicators for each ES and each dimension?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
9	Does the study link and/or integrate the ES dimensions considered in it?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
10	Does the study address sustainability aspects of ES dimensions?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
11	Does the study elucidate uncertainties associated with each of the assessed dimension(s) (and indicator(s))?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
12	Does the study elucidate the (spatial) relations between the assessed dimensions?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise

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768 **Approach for checklist compilation**

769 The checklist has mainly been compiled by relying on the reviewers' own experience in the design,
770 application and communication of ecosystem services assessment, with a specific focus drawn on the
771 concept from the **SEEA-EA framework** (concepts of capacity, potential supply, actual supply (flow),
772 use, and/or demand). Reviewers' own experience was combined as much as possible with guidance
773 extracted from the reviewed literature, although it remained rather incomplete with respect to the
774 link to policy. This diagnostic topic was addressed through twelve questions related to four topics: 1)
775 the identification and **distinction of the concepts** of capacity, potential supply, actual supply (flow),
776 use, and/or demand, 2) the **indicators** used to characterise those concepts in the assessments, 3) the
777 link between the concepts and their **integration in assessments**, 4) the implications of distinguishing
778 and/or using this set of concepts in **policy making**. For each of these four topics, specific points of
779 guidance were extracted by reviewers. These points of guidance were subsequently synthesised and
780 reformulated into checklist questions. The review of the guidance documents and personal knowledge
781 and experience of the experts enable them to identify further checklist questions based on their
782 experience of how research and application of concepts of capacity, potential supply, actual supply
783 (flow), use, and/or demand can feed into decision making.

784 **Expected limitations and possible improvements**

785 There is still some **confusion around the definition of the concepts** in the existing literature, as well as
786 a lack of common understanding. Consequently, there is a risk that (most) concepts are still largely
787 unclear in real world cases. Clear definitions and **examples** of the concepts should be then provided to
788 case studies, to ensure that they are defined and applied in an appropriate and homogenous way by
789 case studies. In addition to providing the proper documentation defining these concepts, further
790 explanation may be needed, e.g., on how to assess them and on the **choice of indicators**, as examples
791 of studies using modelling approaches (wrt tools, indicators) for several of these concepts are still
792 limited. **Testing** on the ground should be conducted with case study practitioners to validate and, when
793 needed, complement and reformulate the check-list questions.

794

795 **S3. Social benefit compatibility of and dimensions of justice in ES**
 796 **assessments**

797

	Checklist	Y	N	N R	Comments
1	Does the study use a participatory approach to ensure that the assessment of ES is rooted in the needs, knowledge and values of the communities or residents relying on these services?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
2	Does the study aim to understand the specific social demands for ES to inform the assessment more effectively?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
3	Does the study identify ES beneficiaries and assess disparities in access and distribution of benefits?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
4	Does the study compare/ validate the scenarios/models/inputs/outputs with local inputs and community perspectives to enhance their credibility?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents and expanded based on reviewer expertise
5	Has a mechanism been established to ensure that local stakeholders can respond to the results and recommendations from the study?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
	ADDITIONAL EXPERT-BASED TOPICS				
6	Does the study investigate the attitudes and perceptions of communities towards specific ES and their importance for well-being?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
7	Does the study customise ES classifications to incorporate local perspectives ?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
8	Does the study identify the most vulnerable or marginalised groups within the study area, and have their needs, perspectives and values been explicitly identified and accounted for?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
9	Does the study acknowledge who has been positively or negatively affected by changes in ES supply or access due to specific interventions?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
10	Does the study account for confounding social, economic, cultural and environmental factors which mediate the relationships between ES and social benefit and justice outcomes?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
11	Does the study evaluate the potential impacts of different policy actions on the distribution of ES benefits among various societal groups?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
12	Have indicators been developed which are specifically social benefit-relevant as determined by the engagement with stakeholders?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise

13	Does the study consider the intergenerational aspects of ES and their implications for future well-being (e.g., impacts of policies or activities)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
14	Does the study explore effective strategies for communicating complex ES-related information to diverse audiences?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
15	Does the study aim to sustain long-term engagement with residents and communities beyond initial policy development (e.g., monitoring and management)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise

798 **Approach to checklist compilation**

799 The checklist aims to address critical gaps identified in existing guidance documents. These gaps likely
800 arise from limitations in understanding the intricate connections between ES and their social
801 implications, including those related to social and environmental justice. For instance, exploring the
802 relationships between biodiversity, ES, and social and environmental justice requires insights from
803 disciplines such as political ecology and diverse social sciences. Moreover, existing guidelines lack
804 information for addressing social and economic inequalities as confounding factors, which are
805 essential when monitoring the effectiveness of models and indicators to demonstrate the connection
806 between ES and human well-being. As a result, the presented checklist, simplified into yes/no
807 questions, has been improved by using experts' perspectives on this topic.

808 **Expected limitations and possible improvement**

809 Despite the above information, the existing checklist has limitations. It assumes that real world cases
810 as end users possess the necessary knowledge and resources to address the complex pathways
811 between ES and social benefits and justice. This assumption includes conducting comprehensive
812 stakeholder mapping and implementing transdisciplinary, cross-sectoral approaches. However, it
813 overlooks the critical need for additional guidance in navigating the complexities of social benefits and
814 justice linked to ES. Moreover, addressing these complexities requires a more comprehensive and
815 inclusive approach, potentially necessitating collaboration across various disciplines and sectors that
816 could be a challenge for some of the projects.

817 Finally, while the checklist is a step towards understanding and assessing the social implications of ES,
818 it is limited in its ability to comprehensively capture the multidimensional aspects of social benefit and
819 justice evaluation that tend to be highly context-specific, highlighting the need for a more collaborative
820 and holistic approach in its development and implementation.

821

S4. Health benefit compatibility of ES assessments

	Checklist	Y	N	N R	Comments
1	Have the views of local stakeholders been incorporated into assessment design?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
2	Have the views of local stakeholders been incorporated into classifications of health-relevant ES ?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
3	Does the study design allow for participatory approaches to ensure that the assessment is appropriately informed and guided by local community knowledge, perspectives, needs and values?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
4	Have distinct pathways between ecosystem structure / function / ecosystem services been explored or identified for those health aspects?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
5	Does the study include an assessment of the stocks and flows of health relevant ES?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
6	Does the study include an assessment of the stocks and flows of health relevant ES?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
7	Has a mechanism been established to ensure that local stakeholders can respond to the results and recommendations from the study?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
	ADDITIONAL EXPERT-BASED TOPICS				
8	Have the views of local stakeholders been factored into the identification of health benefits?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
9	Have key civil society organisations concerned with health care / health inequality / community care / specific health challenges been engaged in the study?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
10	Does the study identify the most vulnerable or marginalised groups within the study area, and have their specific health needs, perspectives and values been explicitly identified and accounted for?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
11	Has a long-term role been identified for local stakeholders, including vulnerable and marginalised groups, in monitoring and managing the results of policy implementation?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
12	Does the study address both immediate cross-community / multi-stakeholder rights, needs and	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise

	values (equity) as well as longer term solutions to securing equitable access (justice)?				
13	Does the study identify specific health issues / outcomes relevant to the geographic area / population / community being studied?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
14	Has the study been guided by the principles of One Health ?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
15	Have specific winners and losers in terms of health-relevant ES access and benefit sharing been identified?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
16	Does the study include an assessment of the wider social, economic, environmental and cultural context within which health-relevant ES supply and demand are determined? (consider climate change, water and air quality, demography, social cohesion, social partnerships, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
17	Have the influences of wider social, environmental, cultural and political issues on health and health inequalities been accounted for?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
18	Does the study identify disparities in access to / benefits from health-benefit ES and attempt to understand the drivers and consequences of such disparities?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
19	Does the study assess the current and / or potential future distributive impacts of policies or activities on ecosystem management?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
20	Does the study account for existing formal and informal governance mechanisms relevant to ES in the study area?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
21	Have the study scenarios / models / inputs / outputs been validated against local knowledge or perspectives?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
22	Have indicators been developed which are specifically relevant to health benefits , as determined by engagement with stakeholders?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
23	Does the study account for confounding social, economic, cultural and environmental factors which mediate the relationships between ES and health outcomes?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
24	Has a mechanism been established to ensure the results of the assessment and related decision-making are effectively communicated to all stakeholders?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise

825 **Approach to checklist compilation**

826 The checklist aims to help to address some of the major gaps identified in the guidance documents
827 during the review; however, it is likely that those gaps reflect gaps in knowledge and expertise (on
828 linkages between ecosystem services and health, and / or on how to assess those connections) in
829 development of those guidance documents, and the **difficulty in synthesising fairly complex cross-**
830 **cutting issues** for which much more research may be required. For example, assessing relationships
831 between biodiversity, ES and infectious disease risk frequently **requires inputs from** eco-epidemiology
832 and various social sciences, and often hinges on perspectives from a **diversity of disciplines or sectors**
833 which may include agriculture, forestry, urban planning, tourism, hydrology, etc. In some cases
834 (particularly relating to mental and physical well-being benefits from recreation) various
835 methodologies have been tried and tested, however where these were incorporated into guidance
836 there was (with only one exception) a lack of guidance on dealing with **confounding factors** and
837 establishing appropriate cross-cutting and benefit-relevant indicators. There was also no guidance on
838 understanding how **social, economic and environmental determinants of health interact**, or how
839 these relate to issues of health inequality and justice.

840 **Expected limitations and possible improvement**

841 In order to limit the checklist to simple yes / no questions, we necessarily assume that the end users
842 will already have the supporting knowledge and resources to identify and unpack the pathways
843 between ES and health, carry out **appropriate stakeholder mapping**, and use that information to build
844 the appropriate trans-disciplinary and cross-sector approaches.

845 Following from the above, we would expect that real world cases may **struggle to identify** the full
846 complement of **health issues** relevant to their projects or project areas, and to explore ES and health
847 linkages in great detail, except perhaps where there is a focus on health promotion through recreation.
848 Improvements would come from a more detailed unpacking of ES-health pathways and paradigms and
849 more detailed guidance on identifying appropriate stakeholders and experts for specific health issues,
850 and further guidance on identifying and addressing related dimensions of justice.

851 See further narrative on compilation approach here:
852 https://docs.google.com/document/d/15dQQIbSi2GMK0sj_np2bdnrYbr3IzvOb/edit

S5. Economic valuation compatibility of ES assessments

	Checklist for economic valuation compatibility	Y	N	N R	Comments
1	Does the study include time and budget for monitoring and engaging in the policy development process ?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
2	Does the study provide training for stakeholders that are likely to take the results forward?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
3	Are the beneficiaries of each ecosystem service identified and quantified (number of beneficiaries, population density, proximity to urban areas etc.) to reflect demand?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
4	Is it possible to expand the geographical scope of the valuation study? If, for example, the original study was for a specific ecosystem, and there is stakeholder demand and funding for scaling up the analysis to the regional or national level.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
5	Is it possible to expand the scope of the valuation study? If, for example, the original study was for a limited set of ES, there might be interest and funding for extending the analysis to other relevant ES.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
6	Does the study discuss the transferability of valuation results to other contexts and regions?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
7	Does the study use a biophysical quantification of ecosystem services as the basis for the economic valuation?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
8	Do the scales (temporal, spatial, beneficiaries) of the biophysical quantification of ecosystem services match the economic valuation?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
9	Does the study describe and distinguish between the total flow of the ecosystem service and changes in the flow (as result of a change in management, extent, condition etc)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
10	Does the study provide information on equity implications?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
11	Does the study assess and address uncertainties associated with the valuation, providing a clear indication of the confidence level in the results?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
12	Does the study develop recommendations on policy responses in light of its findings?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
13	Does the study develop recommendations for appraisal of alternative policy options ?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
14	Does the study organise events open to external audiences to present the results or present at events organised by others (locally, nationally and internationally)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents

15	Does the study organise meetings at which stakeholders can report on progress towards improved ecosystem management?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
16	Does the study publicly report the progress of any further work on ecosystem valuation and, if relevant, keep the study website up to date?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
	ADDITIONAL EXPERT-BASED TOPICS				
17	Does the study involve stakeholders in the scoping and design to enhance relevance?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
18	Does the study assess long-term dynamics in ecosystem capacity, supply and demand in order to measure the sustainability of ES use and values.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
19	Does the study measure the contribution of ES to economic development indicators (e.g. employment, growth)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
20	Have the study results been added to online valuation databases (e.g. ESVD, EVRI)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
21	Have the study results been implemented in a policy or management tool?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise

855

856 **Approach to checklist compilation**

857 The checklist has been compiled by combining guidance drawn from the review process
858 described in Section 3. For each diagnostic question addressed in the review, specific points of
859 guidance were recorded by reviewers as free text in the review form. These points of guidance were
860 subsequently synthesised and reformulated into checklist questions. In addition, other points of
861 guidance from the reviewed studies that do not directly relate to the diagnostic questions were also
862 reformulated into checklist questions. Alongside this process, and with reflection on the points
863 identified through the review, reviewers were invited to include additional checklist questions **based**
864 **on their experience** of how economic valuation research can feed into decision making.

865 **Expected limitations and possible improvement**

866 Some checklist items delve into **technical aspects of economic valuation**, which might be
867 challenging for practitioners in real world cases without specialised knowledge. This complexity
868 necessitates additional explanations or expert guidance for effective comprehension and application.
869 The checklist could also benefit from **practical testing within case studies**; real-world applications can
870 reveal areas for refinement and enhancement. Suggested improvement steps could include: (i) further
871 elaboration and refinement of the checklist questions, informed by practical **testing** and feedback from
872 cases, can enhance clarity and usability; this process should aim to demystify technical aspects and
873 make the valuation more accessible and applicable (ii) establishing a structured **feedback mechanism**
874 to collect and analyse responses, questions, and suggestions from cases can also provide valuable
875 insights for continuous improvement of the checklist, and (iii) providing additional resources, such as
876 **explanatory guides** or access to expert consultation, can assist cases in navigating the more technical
877 aspects of the checklist.

878 For instance, one important limitation is the potential mismatch between the generalised
879 recommendations in the checklist and the **specific, localised needs of individual case studies**. This
880 could lead to a lack of precision in addressing the unique economic aspects of ecosystem services in

881 varied geographical and socio-economic settings. To improve the checklist's applicability, it would be
882 beneficial to incorporate a mechanism for **contextual adaptation**. This could involve providing
883 guidelines on how to modify or augment the checklist based on local economic conditions, stakeholder
884 priorities, and specific ecosystem characteristics. Additionally, the checklist could be enhanced by
885 integrating feedback mechanisms, where practitioners can provide insights based on their on-ground
886 experiences. This process would allow for continuous **refinement of the checklist**, ensuring its
887 relevance and effectiveness in diverse case applications dealing with ecosystem service economic
888 valuation.

889

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891

S6. Spatial scaling and resolution capabilities of ES assessments

	Checklist	Y	N	NR	Comments
1	Is there a process in place for validating the spatial representation of ecosystem services with stakeholders ?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
2	Are the spatial scale and extent of the ecosystem services assessment explicitly stated?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
3	Does the spatial scale of the ES assessment align with the objectives of the management or policy decision it aims to inform?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
4	Are the spatial units used in the assessment clearly defined and justified?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
5	Are spatially explicit indicators used to assess ecosystem services ?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
6	Are spatially explicit indicators used to assess ecosystem condition ?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
7	Is the spatial resolution of the applied ecosystem condition indicators appropriate for the scale of the assessment?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
8	Does the assessment take into account the spatiotemporal dynamics and potential future changes of ES?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
9	Is the spatial resolution of the applied indicators transparently stated?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
	ADDITIONAL EXPERT-BASED TOPICS				
10	Does the assessment incorporate local knowledge or spatial data to enhance the relevance and accuracy of the analysis?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
11	Is the third spatial dimension (e.g. elevation above sea level, relief, or slope) considered in the ES assessment?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
12	Are the methods used to assess ecosystem services appropriate for the complexity of the ecosystem services evaluated?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
13	Are common frameworks (e.g. CICES, Essential variables, MAES) considered in order to homogenise comparisons?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
14	Are maps of the study area recent and do they reliably document recent land use and land cover changes at a relevant spatial scale?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
15	Does the assessment include a sensitivity analysis to understand the effects of varying spatial resolutions?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
16	Are the spatial interdependencies between different ecosystem services within the study area assessed and reported?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise

	Checklist	Y	N	NR	Comments
17	Have potential trade-offs between different spatial scales and their implications on ecosystem services been considered?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
18	Is temporal variability in ecosystem services addressed and documented in the assessment?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
19	Are metadata for spatial scales and resolutions included and following the INSPIRE directive?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
20	Are the limitations on the spatial scales and resolutions clearly identified and justified?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise
21	Are maps of the study area used to visualise the assessment results ?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Based on reviewer expertise

894

895

Approach to checklist compilation

896 The checklist for sensibly addressing spatial scaling and resolution capabilities in a robust ecosystem
897 services assessment has been compiled based on information that has been collected during the
898 review process on guidance documents described in the SELINA M08 report. Insights from established
899 proceedings and practical applications found in the guidance document were queried through closed
900 and free text questions. Furthermore, the reviewers complemented this list based on their own
901 expertise. All assumptions were synthesised and rephrased into 21 questions aiming to ensure a
902 comprehensive, practical, and widely applicable checklist that increases the uptake of findings from
903 ecosystem services assessments in decision-making processes.
904 One key outcome is to **be very transparent and explicit** about the spatial scale, spatial dimensions,
905 spatial resolution, spatial dynamics, applied indicators and frameworks, uncertainties etc. in order to
906 improve the comprehensibility of the assessment.

907

Expected limitations and possible improvement

908 While the checklist provides some aspects to strengthen the spatial scaling and resolution
909 capabilities of ecosystem services assessments, it also contains some potential limitations when
910 applied by practitioners in real world cases. In practice, it is often not the most suitable ES assessment
911 that will be carried out, but a lack of time and resources makes it necessary to evaluate the feasibility
912 in the respective scope. Even if practitioners have decided on the most suitable spatial scale and
913 spatially explicit indicators with a meaningful resolution, the lack of data availability or accessibility
914 may cause an impassable barrier. For now, no guidance on the most suitable, best-use indicators for
915 different spatial scales and different purposes or suggestions for openly available datasets.
916 Additionally, the background and expertise of the practitioners in case studies will most likely be very
917 heterogeneous. Combined with the often inconsistent use and understanding of certain terms and
918 concepts in the ecosystem services domain, we see a high risk of misunderstanding or
919 misinterpretation of certain pieces of advice. Hence, we strongly recommend case studies to use the
920 established Glossaries alongside as a common basis. The creation of meaningful, visually appealing
921 maps (related i.a. to questions 12-13) requires specialised GIS knowledge. Moreover, the map users,
922 notably decision makers, should be cautious when using ecosystem services maps for decision making
923 and ensure they fully understand what is shown and what limitations and uncertainties come with the
924 respective assessment. It is advisable to not only rely on a single map.

925 Some of the questions in this checklist should be mandatory, while some of the more
 926 specialised questions may be optional and depend for example on the purpose of the assessment or
 927 the chosen spatial scale. This could be tested by concrete use cases within case studies and adjusted
 928 in the future. Moreover, the checklists would profit from an iterative feedback mechanism to
 929 constantly refine and update them as well as from good-practice examples potentially linking the
 930 identified questions specifically to the realisation in the assessment to provide clarification.

931

932 S7. Uncertainty assessment

933

	Checklist	Y	N	N R	Comments
1	Does the study validate the ES model? (e.g. model intercomparison, external observations, sensitivity analysis)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
2	Does the study use multiple models leading to a range of outcomes?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
3	Does the study perform model ensembles ?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
4	Does the study use data of appropriate accuracy (temporal, spatial resolution)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
5	Does the study use scenarios ?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
6	Does the study monitor risks ?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
7	Does the study include contingency measures to offset risks of high uncertainty in model outcomes, e.g. risk multipliers.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
8	Does the study use the precautionary principle ?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
9	Does the study communicate uncertainty in the assessment results through levels of uncertainty ? (e.g. <i>Action A is 80% likely to have a certain impact.</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
10	Does the study communicate uncertainty in the assessment results by expressing variation in the results?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
11	Does the study explicitly state the simplifying (model) assumptions and underlying uncertainties?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
12	Does the study collect information during policy implementation? (allowing for iterative improvements of the model)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents
13	Does the study take uncertainty into account by using adaptive planning ?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sourced from reviewed guidance documents

934

935 S8 Full list of publications reviewed on ES assessment guidance

936

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